

DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL TOURISM IN NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Tehmezbeyova K.

*Nakhchivan State University,
Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Azerbaijan*

ABSTRACT

In the article, the explanation of regional tourism is clearly explained, and it is justified that the aspect of safety is the main indicator in regional tourism. It is emphasized that tourism is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon, in which many fields of science, such as economics, business, politics, sociology, etc., are closely interested. In recent years, it is a rapidly developing and profitable field not only in our country, in the region, but even in the whole world. Tourism, as a strong factor of the economy, an effective social institution, and as an indicator of public welfare and culture in society, helps to raise the standard of living and spiritual enrichment of a person. It is the priority direction of the economy in the autonomous republic with high tourism potential. Also, the main directions of the mechanisms driving the development of tourism in the region were shown and the conditions of development were analyzed in detail. The problems of creating a regional brand have been investigated.

Keywords: tourism, regional tourism, development and stimulation of tourism, security, tourist activity.

Introduction. In recent years, one of the most dynamic, rapidly growing, and profitable sectors of the economy has been tourism. This industry is advancing at a high pace and, unlike other sectors, is less affected by economic crises. Tourism, which serves as the economic foundation for many countries, including developed nations, significantly contributes to the state budget. Nature endows some regions with underground and surface resources, and others with rich flora and fauna. However, in certain areas, a wealth of historical traditions, numerous cultural artifacts, diverse climate types, and natural settings have led to the formation of a vast tourism potential in these ancient lands. Beautiful nature, clean air, favorable geography, and boundless mountains and valleys have prompted Azerbaijan to designate the development of national tourism as a priority in the non-oil sector of its economy.

Initiatives undertaken to promote tourism, alongside state programs and improvements in the regulatory and legal framework, affirm this priority. At the national and regional levels, tourism plays a strategically significant role in social policy [1, p. 27-34].

Overall, the tourism sector connects with over 30 other industries, accounting for 8% of global exports and 31% of the world's service market, and employs more than 100 million people, representing one in every ten jobs worldwide. Today, tourism is one of the most profitable and dynamic sectors globally. Approximately 10% of global GDP, investments, job creation, and consumer expenditures are attributed to tourism. According to the latest edition of the International Tourism Barometer by UNWTO (World Tourism Organization), global tourist arrivals in 2023 reached 1.286 billion, almost matching pre-COVID-19 levels from 2019 [7].

Theoretical Aspects of Regional Tourism. Regional tourism fulfills the need for rest and revitalization, allowing individuals in continuous and monotonous work to return refreshed to their jobs, while also generating income and creating employment. To address the worsening income disparity between countries and regions due to globalization, tourism's income-generating and employment-creating

characteristics can be leveraged. Through its geo-economic assets, socio-cultural values, and unique services rooted in non-exportable values, tourism brings foreign currency to regions. A key feature of tourism is its heavy reliance on natural, climatic, historical, folkloric, and cultural values, as these form the fundamental components of the industry. When natural beauty and cultural assets are marketed effectively and responsibly, they provide invaluable revenue streams that positively impact economic stability in countries and regions [2, p. 15-19]. Tourism has gained increasing significance in the global economy as a major sector that directly or indirectly influences people's physical, social, and psychological needs. Although the primary reason for countries' interest in tourism is economic, another key reason is its contribution to improved social welfare. Tourism represents a general social quality and, due to this characteristic, is a multifaceted phenomenon involving economics, business, politics, sociology, and more. While various definitions of tourism exist, a common understanding is that tourism includes travel and temporary accommodation outside one's permanent residence to meet needs for vacation, rest, entertainment, culture, and similar activities [3, p. 15-19]. Regional tourism is not merely an economic event but also a sector that impacts society, thus possessing social, political, and ecological dimensions. Accordingly, when assessing tourism's effects, not only its material and economic outcomes, such as revenue generation and currency inflow, but also its social and cultural reflections should be considered.

Methodology. The economic effects of regional tourism on local development are explained as follows:

1. Employment generated by regional tourism reduces unemployment in rural areas.
2. Tourism increases the inadequate and unstable income of rural populations engaged in agriculture, improving their welfare levels.
3. The development of tourism in rural areas provides employment opportunities for women in various tourism establishments, promoting active participation in the workforce and reducing unemployment.

4. The advancement of regional tourism markets cultural assets, generating additional income for local people and contributing to reduced income inequality.

5. Efficient use of local resources in rural areas promotes economic diversification and strengthens local cooperation and development demands.

6. The growth of regional tourism brings additional income through family entrepreneurship for local communities.

7. Tourism investments in rural areas boost the income of sub-sectors and the construction sector.

8. The gap in development levels between urban and rural areas diminishes.

9. Infrastructure problems in the region are alleviated with the development of regional tourism [4, p. 349].

A distinctive feature of the regional tourism sector is that it belongs to the service sector, relying heavily on labor. No other sector of the economy is as directly connected to people as tourism. While personal activities generate tourism demand, human elements constitute the most crucial factors in responding to this demand. Tourism's labor-intensive nature suggests that the sector can significantly contribute to job creation in the region, facilitating employment for the nation's population and playing an essential role in alleviating unemployment [5, p. 87-96].

Development of Tourism in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Nakhchivan's favorable geographical position, diverse climatic zones, rich cultural heritage, natural therapeutic centers, over 200 mineral springs, unique cuisine, hospitality traditions, and modern advancements are the primary factors supporting tourism development in the autonomous republic. Specially protected natural areas, including Zangezur National Park, the Araz River, Ordubad, and Arpachay Nature Reserves, cover 28% of Nakhchivan's territory [6, p. 626-640]. During the autonomy years, comfortable asphalt roads, water lines, modern infrastructure, uninterrupted gas, electricity, communication services, and high-speed internet were established even in the most remote mountain villages.

Rural tourism has been developed in many settlements such as Bichanak, Kuku, Aghbulag, Nursu, Kechili, Khanagah, and Dirnis. Tourists visiting these areas can also enjoy a wide range of pure ecological products. Winter tourism has also grown in the autonomous republic, with the gbulag Ski Center now operational. As one of the oldest settlements and a region rich in history, Nakhchivan attracts tourists with its cultural and historical heritage. Nakhchivan has great potential for religious tourism, with the Ashabi-Kahf pilgrimage site attracting Muslim visitors from both Azerbaijan and worldwide since independence. The tomb of Prophet Noah is also a notable religious tourism site [7].

Tourism Development Indicators in Nakhchivan. From 2006 to 2023, the number of hotels and hotel-type establishments in the country increased

1.5 times, reaching 657, and revenues from these facilities rose 2.37 times. During this period, the number of employees in Nakhchivan's hotels and similar establishments grew to 332, a 1.6-fold increase[9].

Tax Incentives for Tourism Development. Tax legislation has been amended, and various incentives have been introduced to support entrepreneurship, including those in the tourism sector. With changes to the Tax Code aimed at promoting regional tourism and reducing fixed tax costs, tax incentives for tourism enterprises, such as hotels and sanatoriums, have been established[8]. Effective January 1, 2024, property tax on real estate used in hotel, hotel, and sanatorium activities will be reduced by 75% for three years, excluding the cities of Baku, Sumgait, Khirdalan, and the Absheron district [10].

Conclusion. The study and expansion of tourism resources, providing essential services for tourist leisure, meeting visitor demands, expanding the range of excursions and other cultural activities, aligning with modern standards, studying and sustainably utilizing sanatorium-resort resources, expanding the construction of hotels and other tourism facilities, increasing tourism routes, and developing cultural, ecological, rural green, and recreational tourism underscore the high potential for regional tourism development in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

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